

Students' Perceived Parental Involvement in Their Learning as Correlate of Academic Achievement Among Secondary School Adolescents

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Abstract

This study determined students' perceived parental involvement in their learning as correlate of academic achievement among secondary school adolescents in Anambra State. The research design was correlation survey. Disproportionate stratified sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 825 students from a population of 15781 SS2 students in Anambra state government owned secondary schools. Questionnaires were used to collect data which was administered through direct delivery approach. Research questions 1 and 2 were answered using frequency and percentages while research questions 3 and 4 were answered using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient. The null hypotheses postulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test of correlation analysis. Findings from the study revealed among others that; the relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of in-school adolescents in both English and Mathematics is high and positive. Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made that there is need for parents to collaborate with teachers in order to foster more positive attitudes towards adolescents' learning at school and at home. Also the schools need to work in conjunction with parents to incorporate participative decision making to achieve common goals in adolescents' best interests.

Keywords: Parental involvement, academic achievement, learning, school adolescents, secondary school students.

Introduction

Academic achievement has remained a source of concern to researchers all over the world. This feeling has continued in that the academic achievement of secondary school students deemed to be declining. Statistics have shown that less than 40 percent of candidates who sit for public examination in Nigeria obtained up to credit passes in five subjects which are the minimum academic qualifications for admission into tertiary institutions in Nigeria (Olusegun, 2015). This situation is unacceptable and calls for measures to revamp the system where students' achievement is optimal and acceptable. Optimal academic achievement is a situation whereby students are able to reach their goals of achieving excellence based on their ability, dedication and hard work to learning. Academic achievement according to Awa, Noureen and Naz, (2011) is viewed as examination marks, teachers' given grades and percentiles in academic subjects whereby higher scores indicate better educational attainment. It is the participants' examination grades (grade point average) at the end of a session or program. Similarly, academic achievement could be seen as the level of achievement in a particular field of study.

Based on this, it could be deduced that academic achievement is the degree of attainment of students in tasks or successful accomplishment of program and the test grades obtained from the subjects to which they were exposed to. Furthermore, Von, Hell, Chamarro-Premuzic and Tomas (2011), posited that the dwindle in academic achievement have been linked to many factors including differences in intelligence, personality, parental involvement in students learning and school related factors. They observed that students with higher mental ability as demonstrated by IQ tests and those who are higher in conscientiousness linked to certain factors tend to achieve highly in academic settings.

Nevertheless, the Nigerian society places great emphasis on academic achievements because it is believed to be one avenue for national development. Hence, it is believed that this can only be achieved if students, especially adolescents in schools who are in the citadel of learning get actively involved in pursuits of academic excellence. This however, seems not to be the case presently as researchers such as James (2016) had shown that students' academic achievement is still on decline, especially those of secondary school adolescents. Adolescents on other hand reflects changes on multiple levels which include biological and cognitive growth, social development and family relationships, especially the parent-adolescent relationship and school-teacher relationships (Longmore, Peggy, & Wendy, 2012). Adolescents in the context of this study is conceptualised as children in secondary school level of education, who are in their transitional stage of physical and psychological human development and are under the guidance or care of parents or guardian.

Adolescents in secondary schools tend to experience a significant change compared to primary school. This is perhaps because secondary schools tend to function on a more bureaucratic system with more teachers, peers and curricular choices. In the context of such development, adolescents' academic achievement in some cases, often declines while at the same time, the long-term implication of achievement for educational and occupational attainment tend to increase. The confluence of these development and contextual changes at adolescence increase the risk that some students may not reach their potential and heighten the need to identify sources

of support from parents. In view of this, researchers, for instance, LaRocque, Kleiman and Darling, (2011), reported that parent-child interactions, specifically stimulating and responsive parenting activities, are important influence on a child's academic development. This is because parents are the first teachers a child comes in contact with right from birth. Parents teach the children the first language, pay their school fees, and eventually follow them up through their academic progress, hence it could be said that parents are practically involved with their children's overall learning process.

Studies have shown that, children whose parents are more involved in their education are likely to have higher levels of academic achievement than children whose parents are involved to a lesser degree. The influence of parent involvement on academic achievement has not only been noted among researchers, but also among policy makers who have integrated efforts aimed at increasing parent involvement into broader educational policy initiatives. Parental involvement in the context of this study is therefore seen as activities that parents engage in both at home and at school and positive attitudes parents have towards their child's learning, the school, and the teachers. Furthermore, Marc, Maria and Peter (2012) affirmed that effective, lasting academic achievement is built on caring relationships and warm but challenging classroom and school environments. Therefore, parents, schools and communities all need to work together to create an enabling environment that facilitates healthy development of adolescents.

Students with sense of bonding or belonging to the school, share in its values and would likely perform well academically. Likewise, when parents are directly involved in their children's learning, there tend to be a noticeable difference in the academic pursuit and outcome. Thus this has been a concern to many and research effort has been geared towards investigating such factors as parents' involvement in children's academic outcome. Hence, despite the effort made so far, there is still a lacuna in determining the relationship of these variables among adolescents in secondary schools in Anambra State. With these in mind, this study determined the relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of secondary school adolescents in Anambra State. More specifically, the study determined the scores of secondary school adolescents in their perceived parental involvement in learning, academic achievement scores of secondary school adolescents in English language and Mathematics, the relationship between secondary school adolescents perceived parental involvement in learning and academic achievement in English Language, and the relationship between secondary school adolescents perceived parental involvement in learning and academic achievement in Mathematics in Anambra state.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study.

1. What are the scores of secondary school adolescents on their perceived parental involvement in learning in Anambra state?
2. What are the academic achievement scores of secondary school adolescents in English language and Mathematics?

3. What is the relationship between secondary school adolescents perceived parental involvement in learning and academic achievement in English Language in Anambra state?
4. What is the relationship between secondary school adolescents perceived parental involvement in learning and academic achievement in Mathematics in Anambra state?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were postulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between secondary school adolescents perceived parental involvement in learning and academic achievement in English Language in Anambra state
2. There is no significant relationship between secondary school adolescents perceived parental involvement in learning and academic achievement in Mathematics in Anambra state

Related Literature Reviewed

Figure 1: Conceptual framework on the relationship between secondary school adolescents perceived parental involvement in learning and academic achievement in English language and Mathematics.

The model reviewed for this study Bronfenbrenner’s bioecological model was propounded by Urie Bronfenbrenner and Stephen J. Ceci in 1994. According to this model, understanding human development is contingent on understanding all of the environmental contexts, or subsystems, in which individuals experience growth. This systemic approach to human development is illustrated in two fundamental concepts that form the foundation for

Bronfenbrenner's model. Firstly, the theory postulates that human development occurs through reciprocal interactions between a human organism and the people, resources, activities, and opportunities in their immediate environment. These complex and evolving interactions between an individual and the immediate surrounding environment are referred to as proximal processes in Bronfenbrenner's model.

The Bronfenbrenner incorporated another dimension to this model (that is, the chronosystem) that crosses all four subsystems and describes change over time both in the individual and in historical events. Given the importance of considering children's environmental contexts when examining developmental outcomes (Bronfenbrenner, 2005), The present study used Bronfenbrenner's model as a lens for understanding the academic and social-emotional growth of adolescent. Specially, this study utilized two very important aspects of this model particularly influential subsystem for children at both the microsystem level (that is, the school) and the mesosystem level (that is, the home-school connection). As such, this study took a systemic approach to examining potential risk and protective factors for adolescent in two developmental contexts highly important to student's performance and wellbeing.

Factors that Influence Parental Involvement

There are many factors that influence the type of and level of parental involvement. A deeper understanding of these variables are important to this current study because it provides greater insight regarding the motivational factors that influence why parents become involved. There are factors that influence both how and why parents may become involved in their children's education. Studies show there are many factors that influence parental involvement and such factors have been categorized across both psychological and sociological dimensions. One highly cited research is by Hoover-Dempsey, et al., (2005), who developed a Multi-dimensional model based on four psychological contributing factors of parents becoming involved in their children's education. These factors included:

- a) Parental role construction, or parents' beliefs about what they should do in the context of their child's education;
- b) Parental self-efficacy for helping the child succeed in school, or how much parents believed they could improve children's school outcomes;
- c) Parents' perceptions of general invitations for involvement from the school; and
- d) Parents' life contexts such as socioeconomic status, culture, and family structure.

The influence of parents on children school achievement is well documented in numerous studies. Greater parental involvement at early stage in children's learning, positively affects the child's school performance including higher academic achievement. When schools work together with families to support learning, children tend to succeed not just in school, but throughout life. In-fact the most accurate predictor of a student's achievement in school is not income or social status, but the extent to which that student's family is able to create a home environment that encourages learning and to express high expectations for their children's future careers and become involve in their children's education at schools and in the home (Adewumi, Olojo, & Falemu, 2012).

Importance of Parental Involvement and Students Achievement

Parental involvement is viewed as one of the most effective educational strategies in student achievement and reducing education imbalances. Researchers show parent involvement in their child's education is linked to success (Yan & Lin, 2015), and a key factor related to success for children in school. Accordingly, actively involved parents of students are more likely to follow these processes:

- a) Parents and professionals exchange information
- b) Increased encouragement in the role of the parent
- c) There is a more productive and trusting relationship between the parents and teachers

In the views of Deplanty, Coulter-Kern and Duchane (2007), they believed that adolescents are more positively affected when a relationship is sustained between home and school, and is a critical time when parental involvement is needed even more. Adolescent as a physical, emotional, and intellectual area of concern facing intense preoccupation that brings about questions of personal identity, peer pressure and values. According to The Michigan Department of Education (MDE) early involvement is the most powerful time in a child's life and has the following positive outcomes including; higher grades, tests scores, and graduation, better school attendance, increased motivation, self-esteem, low incidence (suspension, behaviour) and low drug and alcohol use.

Parental Involvement and Homework

According Fan, Williams and Wolters (2012) investigated how different dimensions of parental involvement similarly or differently linked to various constructs of school motivation across ethnic groups. A structural equation modelling approach used to examine the structural relations between student school motivation and parental involvement. The baseline model was applied to each of the samples in order to evaluate the model fit to assess the effects of parental involvement on student school motivation in each ethnic group. Overall, findings support aspects of parental involvement.

Obstacles to Parental Involvement

Parental involvement has been proven by researchers to be instrumental in student success and achievement, yet it faces many obstacles. Research shows that parental involvement begins to decrease after elementary school and is minimal by the time the child reaches high school. There are parents who believe when a child reaches adolescence he should have his own space for independence and growth (De-planty, Coulter-Kern, & Duchane, 2007). In addition, by the time the child reaches high school academics, there are parents who may not have the knowledge or know how of the subject areas which would make the parent feel awkward therefore becoming less involved in their child's educational processes.

DePlanty et al. (2007), described factors that have an impact on parental involvement of students. These factors include:

- a) Parents with little or no social networks, less financial stability, and lower educational levels will have a tendency to become less involved in school activities.

- b) Parents of students are more likely to work outside of the home and less likely to be involved in school activities.
- c) Some students are less likely to have both parents in the home with a college education
- d) Parents of students report they are less involved than those parents of students in general education.

Researchers like carried out by Vera, Isreal, Coyle, Knight-Lynn and Golberger (2012), explored the educational involvement of parents of English learners and examined the relationships among specific barriers such as school involvement, parental involvement, and daily communication with children about their day. Vera et al. found within this study implication for intervention based on a diverse group of immigrant parents and English Learners. The interventions included parent programs, school policy changes, faculty, and professional development on cultural differences. The goal was to increase the involvement of parents of EL children in order to better serve these diverse learners and allow teachers and school officials to be able to communicate with the parents the expectations of their children and parental involvement.

The study also reviewed empirical studies such as: Topor, Keane, Shelton and Calkins (2010) study examined parent involvement in a child's education and potential mechanisms of this association of the child's perception of cognitive competence and the quality of the student-teacher relationship in North Carolina, USA. The study used a sample of 158 seven-year old participants, their mothers, and their teachers. The teacher version of the Parent-Teacher Involvement Questionnaire (INVOLVE) was used to assess parent involvement; the Student-Teacher Relationship Scale (STRS) consists of 28 items that measure aspects of the relationship between the student and teacher, while The Pictorial Scale of Perceived Competence and Social Acceptance for Young consists of 24 items that measure four domains of self-concept. Two measures of academic performance were used. The Wechsler Individual Achievement Test-Second Edition and the Academic Performance Rating Scale (APRS). Data were gathered from the child and the child's mother during two visits to the laboratory and from the child's teacher during one visit to the child's school. Four regression analyses were performed to test each potential mediator and variables considered as co-variants were controlled for in all regression equations. A multiple mediation model was used to examine if both potential mediators jointly reduce the direct effect of parent involvement on a child's academic performance and to better understand the unique contribution of each individual mediator when the other mediator is controlled. Results indicated a statistically significant association between parent involvement and a child's academic performance, over and above the impact of the child's intelligence. A multiple mediation model indicated that the child's perception of cognitive competence fully mediated the relation between parent involvement and the child's performance on a standardized achievement test. The quality of the student-teacher relationship fully mediated the relation between parent involvement and teacher ratings of the child's classroom academic performance. Furthermore, Chohan and Khan (2010) examined the impact of educational support given by the parents on the academic achievement and on the self-concept of grade 4 public school students. The study was descriptive in nature and with quantitative methodology. The data regarding

parental support, its effects on the academic achievement and the self-concept were collected from a sample (N =305) of grade 4 students in the urban primary and elementary public schools. The sample students who have or have not parental support were compared on two measures, (a) the annual school result report and, (b) the self-concept scale. The self-concept was measured twice i.e. before one month of annual school examination and after one month of announcement of annual results. The findings of the study revealed that parents' contribution to their children's education has a consistent and positive effect on academic achievement.

Method

The research design for this study is correlational survey design. The study was carried out in Anambra state. Anambra state was deemed appropriate for this study because due to observation secondary school enrolment in the state is one of the highest in the country. So classes in most schools are overpopulated, thereby posing a challenge for teachers surmount and be successful. On the other hand, parents of adolescents' have the reputation of devoting significant part of their lives to their child's upbringing. Nevertheless, this seems not to have been empirically established, hence the researcher thus considered Anambra state appropriate for this study. The population for this study comprised 15,781 senior secondary school II students in Anambra state. The sample for this study is 825 students', this sample was drawn using the multistage sampling procedure.

The instrument for data collection comprised of parental involvement questionnaire developed by the researcher from different literatures reviewed and a score sheet of their academic achievement in English language and Mathematics. The questionnaire has a 4-point response options which from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from the department of guidance and counselling and one validate from the department of measurement and evaluation. The internal consistency of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha statistics and yielded a coefficient of 0.78. the administration of the instrument was done through direct delivery approach. Data relating to research question 1 was analyzed using aggregate scores and percentage, while research question 2 and 3 was analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. More so, data relating to hypothesis 1 and 2 was analysed using t-test for correlation analysis. The decision rule for judging the parental involvement is as follows:

1.00 – 1.45 = Very Low parental involvement

1.50 – 2.45 = Low parental involvement

2.50 – 3.45 = High parental involvement

3.50 – 4.00 = Very High Parental involvement

The decision rule for judging the resulting correlation coefficient was:

Very low positive or negative relationship = + or - 0.00 to 0.20,

Low positive or negative relationship = + or - 0.20 to 0.40,

Moderate positive or negative relationship = + or - 0.40 to 0.60,

High positive or negative relationship = + or - 0.60 to 0.80,

Very high positive or negative relationship = + or - 0.80 and above.

Results

The results of the study were presented as follows;

Research Question 1: What are the scores of secondary school adolescents on their perceived parental involvement in learning in Anambra state?

Table 1: Range and scores of secondary school adolescents on their perceived parental involvement in learning (N=825)

Parental Involvement Scores	N	%	Remark
19 – 34	402	48.73	Low parental involvement
35 – 54	388	47.0	High parental involvement
55 – 76	35	4.24	Very high parental involvement

Analysis on Table 1 shows that 48.73% of 825 secondary school adolescents rated their parental involvement low (19-34) as indicated on the table, 47.0% and 4.24% of secondary school adolescents rated their parental involvement high (35-54) and very high (55-76) respectively.

Research Question 2: What are the academic achievement scores of secondary school adolescents in English language and Mathematics?

Table 2: Range and academic achievement scores of secondary school adolescents in English language and Mathematics (N=825)

Range of Scores	English Language		Mathematics		Remarks
	N	%	N	%	
70 & above	110	13.33	98	11.88	Excellent
50 – 69	165	20	204	17.21	Very Good
40 – 49	506	61.3	411	58.31	Good
0 – 39	44	5.33	42	5.09	Poor

Table 2 reveals that 110 (13.33%) adolescents with the scores ranging from 70 and 100 have Excellent scores in English language, while 165 (20.0%) of them who scored between 50 and 69 have Very Good scores in English language. Also the 506 (61.3%) who scored between 40 and 49 have Good scores, while 44(5.33%) who scored between 0 and 39 have Poor achievement. Similarly, table 3 further reveals that 98 (11.88%) adolescents with the scores ranging from 70 and 100 have Excellent Achievement scores in Mathematics, while 204 (17.21%) of them who scored between 50 and 69 have Very Good Achievement scores in Mathematics. Also the 411 (58.31%) who scored between 40 and 49 have Good Achievement scores, while 42(5.09%) who scored between 0 and 39 have Poor achievement.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between secondary school adolescents perceived parental involvement in learning and academic achievement of secondary school adolescents in English Language in Anambra state?

Table 3: Relationship between parental involvement in learning and academic achievement of secondary school adolescents in English language.

N	Correlation Coefficient (r)	Remark
825	.959	Very High Relationship

Table 3 shows that a Pearson product moment correlation was computed to determine the relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of secondary school adolescents in English language. On the whole, there is a very high positive correlation between parental involvement and academic achievement of secondary school adolescents in English language ($r = .959, n = 825$).

Research Question 4: What is the relationship between secondary school adolescents perceived parental involvement in learning and academic achievement in Mathematics in Anambra state?

Table 4: relationship between secondary school adolescents perceived parental involvement in learning and academic achievement in Mathematics.

N	Correlation Coefficient (r)	Remark
825	.941	Very High Relationship

Table 4 shows the nature of relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of secondary school adolescents in Mathematics. The analysis reveals a very high positive correlation between parental involvement and academic achievement of secondary school adolescents in Mathematics ($r = .941, n = 825$).

Hypotheses Testing

The following null hypotheses were postulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between secondary school adolescents perceived parental involvement in learning and academic achievement in English Language in Anambra state.

Table 5: Test of significance of relationship between parental involvement in learning and academic achievement of secondary school adolescents in English language

Correlation Coefficient (γ)	N	df	α	t-calculated	t-critical	Decision
.96	825	823	.05	98.4	1.960	Reject

Table 5 reveals that the t calculated value 98.4 is greater than the t critical value of 1.960 at .05 alpha level ($98.4 > 1.960$). this indicates that the null hypothesis was rejected that there is a significant relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of secondary school adolescents in English language.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between secondary school adolescents perceived parental involvement in learning and academic achievement in Mathematics in Anambra state.

Table 6: test of significance of relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of secondary school adolescents in Mathematics.

Correlation Coefficient (γ)	N	df	α	t-calculated	t-critical	Decision
.94	825	823	.05	77.8	1.960	Reject

Analysis on Table 9 shows that the value of t-calculated (77.8) is greater than the value of t-critical (1.960) at .05 alpha level ($77.8 > 1.960$). Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected that there is a significant relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of secondary school adolescents in Mathematics.

Discussions

Findings from the study revealed that majority of the secondary school adolescents rated their parental involvement low. What this means is that in the opinion of secondary school adolescents, the parents are not totally involved in their academic activities. The reason for this could be explained in terms of many factors that influence parental involvement, and such factors, according to Hoover-Dempsey et al. (2005) have been categorized across both psychological and sociological dimensions. These factors Hoover-Dempsey et al. (2005) noted include; parents' beliefs about what they should do in the context of their child's education; parental self-efficacy for helping the child succeed in school, or how much parents believed they could improve children's school outcomes; parents' perceptions of general invitations for involvement from the school; and parents' life contexts such as socioeconomic status, culture, and family structure.

Similarly, the finding of the study revealed that majority of the secondary school adolescents has low achievement in both English Language and Mathematics. This means that the secondary school adolescents performed below average in both subjects. This goes on to affirm the notion that there is a general low academic achievement among the secondary school adolescents. The finding is in line with Olusegun (2015), whose findings supported the assertion that based on the available statistics; the academic achievement of students has remained on decline. More so, findings from the study revealed that there is a high positive relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of secondary school adolescents in both English language and Mathematics in Anambra State. The findings showed that the low parental involvement led to a poor academic achievement among the secondary school adolescents. What this implies is that there is a connection between parental involvement and students' academic achievement, such that when parents are involved in their children's academic activities like; monitoring how they do their homework and assist where they can, ensuring that they spend more time on their studies than they do doing other things like watching television; making sure they complete all their assignments on time and ensuring it is done well, among others, there will likely be an improvement in the academic achievement of the students.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study and the discussions made, the following conclusions were made: There is a significant high positive relationship between parental involvement

academic achievement of secondary school adolescents in English language and Mathematics in Anambra State. These findings suggest that variables that are consistently associated with high academic achievement among others include parental involvement. Since adolescents in secondary schools spend significant part of their time in a classroom (about 7 ½ hrs a day, 5 days a week, and 36 weeks a year), there is need to help them feel connected to the school environment to succeed academically. On the contrary, the students in school only spend 45 to 90 minutes per day with each teacher, so it is nearly impossible for them to unconsciously transmit all of the knowledge the children need to get to them in that time frame. Therefore, unarguably it becomes imperative for parents to fulfil their first job, which is to be a teacher to their children.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study and conclusions drawn, it was recommended that;

1. Since there is a positive high relation between parents involvement in their child's learning and their academic achievement, parents should increase their effort in being involved in their children's learning by taking the leading role in supporting their children's educational endeavours, like take home assignments since they are the first educators to expose them to the academic world.
2. Parents should endeavour to work closely with their children's school in order to build a strong parent-teacher partnership to enhance their connection with the school and in order to improve on their academic achievement.

REFERENCES

- Adewumi, M. G.; Olojo, O. J.; Falemu, F. A. (2012). Roles of parent on the academic performance of pupils in elementary schools. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Science*, 2(1), 2222-6990.
- Awa, R. I. (2011). A study of the relationship between motivation, self-concept and achievement in English and Mathematics at secondary level. *International education Studies*, 4(3), 72-79.
- Bronfenbrenner, U. (2005). *Making human beings human: Bioecological perspectives on human development*. Thousand Oaks : CA Sage Publications Ltd.
- De-planty, J., Coulter-Kern, R., & Duchane, K. A. (2007). Perceptions of parents involvement in academic achievement. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 100(6), 361-368.
- Fan, W., Williams, C. M., & Wolters, C. A. (2012). Parental involvement in predicting school motivation: Similar and different effects across ethnic groups. *Journal of Educational Research*, 105(1), 21-35.
- Hoover-Dempsey, K., Battiato, A., Wakker, J., Reed, R., Dejong, J., & Jones, K. (2005). Parental involvement in homework. *Educational Psychologist*, 36(3), 195-209.

- James, B. R. (2016). Securing the organization future by learning from its past. *Journal of Global Business and Organizationa Excellence*, 35(4), 67-75.
- LaRocque, M., Kleiman, I., & Darling, S. (2011). Parental Involvement: The missing link in school achievement. *Preventing School Failure*, 55(3) , 115-122.
- Longmore, M. A., Peggy, C., & Wendy, D. (2012). *Parent-child relationships in adolescence: A handbook of family theories*. Routledge: Abingdon.
- Marc, B. W., Maria, R. R., & Peter, S. S. (2012). Enhancing academic performance and social and emotional competence with the ruler feeling words curriculum. *Journal of Learning and Individual Difference*, 22(2), 218-224.
- Olusegun, F. (2015). Retrieved from). <http://www.myschoolgist.com.ng/ng/check-waec-result-waec-may-june-result/>
- Vera, E. M., Isreal, M., Coyle, L., Knight-Lynn, L., & Golberger, N. (2012). Exploring the educational involvement of parents of English learners. *School Community Journal*, 22(2), 183-202.
- Von, S. S.-P. (2011). The hungry mind: Intellectual curiosity is the third pillar of academic performance. *Perspective on Psychological Science*. 6 (6), 85-104.
- Yan, W., & Lin, O. (2015). Parental involvement in mathematics achievement: Contrast across racial and ethnic groups. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 99(2), 116-127.